

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF DEVELOPING COMPETENCE IN DIGITAL CONTENT CREATION BASED ON THE INTEGRATION OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES AND PROFESSIONAL SUBJECTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16249925>

Abstract. *This article analyzes the development of competence in digital content creation based on the integration of information technologies and professional subjects, as well as its theoretical and methodological foundations within the educational system. A systematic model is proposed for enhancing this competence through an innovative approach grounded in the TPACK model and the "Pedagogical Wheel" concept. The article highlights opportunities for fostering students' independent, creative, and digital thinking skills through an integrative approach. Furthermore, it explains the content of digital competence, tools for its development, and mechanisms of integration from both pedagogical and technological perspectives.*

Keywords: *digital content, information technologies, professional subjects, integration, digital competence, TPACK model, pedagogical wheel, innovative education, digital learning, learning environment, software tools, multimedia tools.*

Digital technologies are emerging in the modern world as an innovative environment that allows people to effectively use advanced technologies. The rapid development of digital technologies is creating the basis for the formation of new pedagogical approaches in the modern education system. The digital education system is fundamentally different from traditional educational methods in its essence and offers new opportunities. In particular, new opportunities for digital education - distance learning, online platforms, artificial intelligence-based learning systems, adaptive learning modules and the use of digital content - are serving as an important factor in the complete transformation of traditional educational processes and teaching methods into a new digital model. These opportunities are making teaching methods interactive, multimodal (video, audio, animation, text), as well as flexible to the individual needs of the student. As a result, the opportunities for improving the quality of the educational process, increasing the activity of students, and developing their independent thinking and creative potential are expanding. Therefore, improving the educational process in a modern digital environment is becoming a strategic necessity. In particular, the formation of digital content creation competence in the system of professional disciplines has become one of the urgent tasks of today. In the conditions of today's digital economy, each representative of the industry is required not only to be able to use information technologies, but also to have the skills to create digital content appropriate to their professional activities. From this point of view, the issue of developing students' digital content creation competence through the integration of information technologies with professional disciplines is of scientific and practical importance [1].

As part of the scientific research, an innovative pedagogical model was developed based on the integration of information technologies and professional disciplines, aimed at improving students' digital content creation competence. This model is designed based on the TPACK (Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge) concept and the “Pedagogy Wheel” and allows for the use of technological tools in the educational process in a meaningful and pedagogically integrated manner. The model was developed based on an in-depth analysis of the specific features of the higher education system of Uzbekistan - the content of education integrated with professional areas in the field of disciplines, the state of digital infrastructure and the level of student preparation. Through this model, the stages, methods and tools that serve to effectively form the competence of creating digital content have been systematized.

Through the formation of the competence of creating digital content, students will have the opportunity to independently and creatively express their knowledge, skills and qualifications in professional areas based on modern digital tools. This will increase their level of preparation for professional activities and serve to provide personnel meeting the requirements of the modern market. In the effective organization of this process, approaches such as combining the content of professional disciplines with information technologies, applying project-based educational methods using digital tools, and introducing interactive platforms into the educational process play an important role. Therefore, the development of theoretical foundations for the formation of digital content creation competence and their implementation in practice is one of the strategic directions of the education system today [2].

The rapid development of information technologies in the education system creates the need for their integration into professional disciplines. This process requires not only the digitization of educational materials, but also the modernization of the process of preparing students for professional activity. Therefore, the integration of the content of professional disciplines with information technologies is one of the important factors in the formation of digital competencies in students. Let us analyze the concept of integration that gave rise to these factors.

Chapaev N.K. In the research work “Theoretical and methodological foundations of pedagogical integration”, he writes that integrative pedagogical activity is a holistic system that includes an organizational set of structural, structural and content indicators, the conditions of its functioning are connected with the presence of mechanisms and technological infrastructure, it is a driving force that includes a technological chain of tools, it is necessary to create new integrative pedagogical formations, correct and adapt the current results of the integrative pedagogical process [3]. A.I. Avazboev puts forward the idea that integration is “the process of combining individual components into a whole, creating a new feature”. In this, integration is interpreted as a process and described in sufficient detail [4].

Gafforov F.H. approves of the German dual education system as a good system for integrating theoretical and practical training programs in the training of specialists in vocational education. He writes in his research that the dual system is considered an effective and economical system for personnel policy, and the closer the training is to practice, the greater the benefits for the enterprise and the student [6].

From the scientific research works based on the integration of information technologies and professional disciplines in the effectiveness of education in Russia: A. Rodinov's research identified the possibilities of using information technologies in the teaching of chemistry [7]. V.N. Likhachev noted the need to replace traditional methods of teaching students with modern

technologies in order to increase the level of knowledge of students[8], A.C. Artemyeva wrote about the creation of electronic textbooks for individual preparation of students in order to achieve high results in lessons[9]. E.Yu. Zashivalova focused on the methodology of computer-based teaching of students, the form of teaching chemistry on a computer, teaching chemistry using a computer[10]. Based on these analyses, we define “Integration is a multi-level evolutionary process that strengthens the internal and external interconnections between various systems, structures or functional components, representing a complex, flexible, stable and dynamic set of changes. It is realized through the processes of integration, coordination, adaptation and transformation”.

It is important to take into account digital competence in the competence of students to create digital content based on the integration of information technologies and professional disciplines. Digital competence is a set of skills necessary for successful work in modern society. It allows each person to fully use digital tools in their daily and professional life, which increases productivity and quality of life. Digital competence is the ability of a person to effectively use digital technologies and tools. This competence includes not only technical skills, but also the ability to work with digital tools for various purposes, think creatively, solve problems, analyze information, and communicate online. Rahmawati S. defines digital competence as follows: “Digital competence is a set of knowledge and skills necessary to solve problems and issues using information technologies and digital media” [11]. M.E. Mamarajabov in his dissertation: “Digital learning process is an educational process based on the use of digital technologies in digital education, aimed at developing digital competencies, taking into account individual and collective learning activities of students. Digital competencies are a set of knowledge, skills, and competencies necessary for the successful solution of professional problems” [12].

In the education system, digital content is a set of educational, control, and training materials based on information technologies that are distributed electronically through special channels for use on digital devices (computers, tablets, smartphones). The main types of modern digital content are text, game, video, and audio didactic materials [13].

The development and promotion of new tools to train and support capable, motivated, and highly qualified future teachers, pedagogical staff, and school principals for the digital society, as well as to improve their continuous professional development and ensure that teachers receive quality education based on scientific research, are relevant in today's rapidly changing world [14]. The introduction of advanced information technologies, the development of innovative teaching methods, and the training of personnel suitable for the digital society are among the important directions of this decree.

In the context of digital education, the training of teachers for professional activity has a number of important differences from the traditional one: mobility, focus on innovation as a principle responsible for responding to the challenges of the time; identification of the central personality of the student who seeks to build his own educational trajectory within the framework of the technology of an open model of asynchronous individual education, which implements continuous education using digital educational environment tools in the innovative system of teacher training[12]. M.P.D.Prensky conducted a study on the importance of digital content creation competence in education, and discussed in detail how digital content creation competence affects the education system, how it increases the effectiveness of the educational process, and how it develops students' digital literacy

Digital content creation competence is a complex set of skills that includes the ability of a person to create, edit, organize and distribute meaningful information products related to pedagogical, scientific or professional activities in a purposeful manner using digital technologies. This competence requires modern teachers, students and specialists to work effectively with information and communication technologies, develop interactive and multimedia content, accurately assess their educational and educational value and correctly present them in a digital environment. At the same time, digital content creation competence is not limited only to technical skills, but also includes complex professional qualities such as creative thinking, media literacy, information security and adherence to ethical standards. The process of creating digital content is a complex and multi-stage process that requires a systematic approach, creative thinking and effective use of modern information technologies. Software tools used in the process of content creation serve to prepare information products in various areas. Such programs include applications designed to develop didactic materials, audio and video editors, graphic and animation tools, as well as complex platforms that allow the integration of multimedia products. These software complexes play an important role in the formation of effective educational resources in a digital educational environment. In the process of creating digital content, the technological development stage is a central component, in which educational materials are developed based on the integration of modern technical means, software and pedagogical technologies. This includes practical activities such as designing, visualizing, interactivity and testing digital content. A number of multimedia and pedagogical software tools are used in the creation of digital content. Programs such as Adobe Captivate, Camtasia, iSpring Suite, Bandicam and Biteable allow you to create video tutorials, interactive presentations, screen recordings and animated videos. These tools are mainly used to develop audio-video content, insert visual annotations and digitize lesson processes. In graphic design, visual materials, and animations, modern platforms that provide aesthetic appearance and functional expressiveness of educational content are widely used - Microsoft PowerPoint, Canva, Biteable, Prezi, Adobe Illustrator, and Figma. While Canva and PowerPoint are designed to create static and dynamic slides through an easy interface and ready-made templates, Biteable and Prezi have advantages in creating interactive presentations and animations. Adobe Illustrator and Figma are used for complex graphic elements, icons, vector designs, and user interface design. In creating interactive tests and assessment tools, platforms such as MyTestX, Hot Potatoes, H5P, Quizizz, Google Forms, and Typeform, which allow students to consolidate and monitor their knowledge, are effective. While MyTestX and Hot Potatoes are designed to create traditional types of tests, H5P allows you to create interactive videos, drag-and-drop exercises, and multimodal tests. Quizizz, Google Forms and Typeform are widely used in organizing real-time tests, questionnaires and reflection exercises in online format. Also, pedagogical platforms such as Moodle, Google Classroom, Nearpod, ClassPoint, Kahoot!, Edmodo play an important role in presenting content and integrating it into the learning process. These tools allow diagnosing the level of knowledge of students, managing learning activities and providing teaching in an interactive environment. In conclusion, it should be said that the development of digital content creation competence, which is being formed in the digital educational environment based on modern requirements, is a necessary factor for improving the quality of the educational process, strengthening professional training and individualizing education. The pedagogical model, developed on the basis of the integration of information technologies and professional disciplines, serves the comprehensive development of digital

competencies in students. This model considers digital technologies not only as a technical tool, but also as a harmonizing force in terms of content and methodology. The development of creativity, media literacy, information security, as well as ethics and communication skills, is essential in building digital content creation competence. As a result, this approach serves to shape teachers and students as competitive personnel suitable for the modern digital society.

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